

2:6-DIARYL-3-ETHOXYCARBONYL-4-PIPERIDONES AND THEIR
N-METHYL DERIVATIVES

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Six new *N*-methyl-2:6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones have been synthesised and converted into pyrazolone derivatives.

Noller *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3853) developed a satisfactory procedure by which they prepared a number of substituted 4-piperidones by condensing ethyl acetoacetate with aromatic aldehydes and ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid.

The aim of the present investigation was to extend this method in continuation of our earlier work (Bhargava *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 105) to the synthesis of some new 2:6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones with a view to converting them into *N*-methyl derivatives of possible therapeutic value as analgesics and antipyretics.

p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde, cinnamaldehyde, *o*-chloro-, *p*-chloro-, *m*-nitro- and *p*-nitro-benzaldehydes, piperonal and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been employed in the preparation of 2:6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones. The maximum yield of 90% has been obtained in the case of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde derivatives and minimum yield of 41% in the case of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde derivative. Two of these 4-piperidones have been converted into pyrazolone derivatives.

Condensation with dimethyl sulphate in acetone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate has yielded *N*-methyl-2:6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones and these on treatment with phenylhydrazine have been converted into pyrazolone derivatives, which may show a complex pattern of pharmacodynamic behaviour.

Thus, the structure of *N*-methyl-4-piperidones has been corroborated by the preparation of the characteristic derivatives and analyses.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:6-Diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones.—A mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (0.25 M), aromatic aldehyde (0.5 M) and ammonium acetate (0.5 M) in glacial acetic acid (35 c.c.) was heated under reflux at 100-150° for 1-2.5 hours. The product was isolated following the procedure of Bhargava *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The data regarding properties and analyses are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Aldehyde condensed.	Yield.**	Solvent of cryst.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
							Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy-B*	90%	Benzene	White	157°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ N	3.86	3.89
2.	Cinnamaldehyde	81	Pet. ether	Pale yellow	126°	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	3.73	3.75
3.	<i>o</i> -chloro-B	73	Chloroform	Black	95°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ NCl ₂	3.52	3.57
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro-B	72	Do	Yellow	180°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ NCl ₂	3.54	3.57
5.	<i>m</i> -Nitro-B	82	Methanol	Yellow	138°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₃	10.10	10.16
6.	<i>p</i> -Nitro-B	79	Acetone	Dirty yellow	110°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₃	10.08	10.16
7.	Piperonal	84	Pet. ether	Yellow	86°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₃ N	3.42	3.40
8.	2-Hydroxy-1 naphthaldehyde	41	Methanol	Greenish black	191°	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₅ N	3.08	3.10

* B denotes benzaldehyde.

** Yield is based on the liberation of 4-piperidones from their hydrochlorides.

1-Phenyl-3 : 4-(2' : 6'-diaryl)-piperidopyrazolone-5.—The appropriate piperidone (0.1 M) and phenylhydrazine (0.1 M) were refluxed in an oil-bath at 125-40° for 1.5-3 hours. After the reaction, the contents were cooled and treated with glacial acetic acid with stirring. The precipitate thus obtained was crystallised from a suitable solvent. The data regarding properties and analyses are mentioned in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Aldehydes.*	Solvent of cryst.	% Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
							Found.	Calc.
1.	Acetone	54	White	125°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	10.46	10.52	
3.	Chloroform	90	Brown	175°	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ ON ₃ Cl ₂	9.70	9.63	

* The number corresponds to the respective aldehydes shown in Table I.

N-Methyl-2 : 6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones.—The piperidone (0.2 M) in acetone (25 c.c.), dimethyl sulphate (0.2 M) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.3 M) were refluxed on a water-bath for 3 hours. At the end of the reaction, the contents were poured into ice-cold water (100 c.c.) and stirred well. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from alcohol. Relevant data are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Aldehydes*.	% Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
1.		82	White	145°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N	3.74	3.79
2.		86	Do	130°	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ O ₅ N	3.68	3.65
5.		87	Brick-red	96°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₇ N ₃	9.80	9.83
6.		78	Red	116°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₇ N ₃	9.85	9.83
7.		69°	Yellow	102°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₇ N	3.31	3.29
8.		14	Do	136° (decomp.)	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₅ N	3.00	2.99

* The number corresponds to the respective aldehydes shown in Table I.

1-Phenyl-3:4 (N-methyl-2': 6'-diaryl)-piperido-pyrazolone-5.—The corresponding piperidone (0.1 M) and phenylhydrazine (0.1 M) were refluxed in an oil-bath at 125-140° for 2-2.5 hours. After the reaction, the contents were cooled and treated with absolute alcohol. Most of the tarry matter dissolved leaving behind greyish white solids. These were filtered and crystallised from suitable solvents. The data regarding properties and analyses are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Aldehydes.	Refluxed for.	at.	% Yield.	Solvent of cryst.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
								Found.	Calc.
No. 2.	2.5 hrs.	125°	75	Acetone	White	285° (decomp.)	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃	9.63	9.69
3.	2.0	130°	85	Ether- alcohol	Black	170°	C ₂₈ H ₃₁ O ₅ N ₅	14.90	14.66
7.	2.5	125°	64	Chloroform	Brown	173°	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₃	9.00	8.95
8.	2.5	140°	50	Ether	Black	183°	C ₃₃ H ₃₇ O ₃ N ₃	8.12	8.18

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities.

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Received June 24, 1958.